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Crop and resource management

Physiology and plant nutrition

Effects of nitrogen and potassium nutrition during late growth stage of rice on translocation of ¹⁴C and grain yield

Yong-Rui Wang and Ying-Jie Zhang, Biology Department, School of Life Sciences, Sun Yat Sen University, Guangzhou 510275, China

The effect of late N and K application on the translocation of ¹⁴C from the flag leaf and on grain yield was studied. Four seedlings each of the hybrids W6154s/DFo and W6154s/Tie-San-Ai (F₁) were transplanted into 15-liter pots. Fertilizer treatments were no fertilizer control, basal fertilizer only, basal fertilizer + topdressed N (urea) and K (K₂SO₄) at 5-7 d before panicle exertion, and basal fertilizer + topdressed N (urea) and K (K₂SO₄) at 5-7 d after panicle exertion. Basal fertilizer consisted of 2 g each of urea, calcium superphosphate, and potassium sulfate/pot.

¹⁴C-glucose (40-60 µci/ml) was sprayed at 0.05 ml/flag leaf for selected tillers at the milky stage. Two days later, plants were sampled and separated into panicles, flag leaves, rest of green leaves, and culms. The radioactivity of each part was measured using a scintillation counter and expressed as count per minute (CPM). The percentage of ¹⁴C exported from the flag leaf was calculated as:

$$\frac{\text{Total CPM of plant} - \text{CPM in the flag leaf}}{\text{Total CPM of plant}} \times 100$$

The percentage of ¹⁴C translocated to the panicle was calculated as:

$$\frac{\text{CPM of panicle}}{\text{Total CPM of plant} - \text{CPM of flag leaf}} \times 100$$

The ¹⁴C accumulation percentage (AP) in the panicle, which reflects higher photosynthetic rate, more translocation of assimilates, larger sink capacity, and a

Table 1. Effect of N and K nutrition at late growth stage on the percentage of ¹⁴C exported from the flag leaf (1), translocated to the panicle (2), and ¹⁴C accumulation percentage [(1×2)/100] (3) at milky stage of two rice hybrids.

Treatment	W6154s/DFo			W6154s/Tie-San-Ai		
	1	2	3	1	2	3
No fertilizer	50.38	44.88	22.61	57.62	42.43	24.45
Basal fertilizer	73.82	70.83	52.29	62.43	54.63	34.11
Basal fertilizer + N and K topdressing before panicle exertion	88.38	81.70	72.21	87.85	78.80	69.23
Basal fertilizer + N and K topdressing after panicle exertion	78.88	71.60	56.48	77.59	84.20	65.33

Table 2. Effect of N and K nutrition at late growth stage on yield components and grain yield of two hybrids.

Treatment	Filled spikelets/panicle (no.)	Filled spikelets (%)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Grain yield (g/hill)
<i>W6154s/DFo</i>				
No fertilizer	102.5	88.5	22.60	8.85 ± 0.48
Basal fertilizer	110.3	93.5	22.50	11.72 ± 0.77
Basal fertilizer + N and K topdressing before panicle exertion	119.7	98.4	24.40	15.80 ± 0.92
Basal fertilizer + N and K topdressing after panicle exertion	120.9	97.0	24.30	14.70 ± 0.69
<i>W6154s/Tie-San-Ai</i>				
No fertilizer	108.7	65.8	24.50	8.31 ± 0.52
Basal fertilizer	123.7	78.7	24.00	12.62 ± 0.68
Basal fertilizer + N and K topdressing before exertion	130.9	83.1	25.30	14.69 ± 0.88
Basal fertilizer + N and K topdressing after exertion	137.1	83.4	25.80	15.49 ± 0.75

better source-sink relationship, was equal to the ratio of CPM in the panicle to total CPM in the plant multiplied by 100.

The percentages of ¹⁴C exported from the flag leaf and translocated to the panicle and the AP in the topdressed plants were all higher than those that received no fertilizer or only basal fertilizer (Table 1). Filled spikelets per panicle, filled spikelet percentage, 1,000-grain weight, and grain yield of the two rice hybrids were all greater in the topdressed plants than in the control plants (Table 2).

The results indicate that topdressing N and K at around panicle exertion is a good cultural practice because it enhances translocation of assimilates from the flag leaf to the panicle during ripening. ■

Fertilizer management —inorganic sources

Response of rice to nitrogen and zinc application in a calcareous situation

A. K. Singh, S. Thakur, and S. K. Singh, Agronomy Department, Rajendra Agricultural University, Pusa Samastipur, Bihar 848125, India

The calcareous soils of northern Bihar, India, are markedly deficient in Zn. We applied N at different levels (0, 50, 100, and 150 kg/ha) with and without Zn to study the effect on grain and straw yields, N and Zn uptake, chlorophyll content, and net return obtained.